

The ‘religion’ of Mozart’s Requiem and aesthetic autonomy in its early reception

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ABSTRACT This paper attempts to identify how Mozart’s Requiem came to be regarded as an aesthetically autonomous work. By exploring reception in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries in conjunction with the emergence of the movement of *Kunstreligion* and of the ‘musical work’, this paper proposes that Mozart’s Requiem played a key role in the ontological shift of how musical works were received.

Through the course of this seminar I will be attempting to illustrate how Mozart’s Requiem achieved a quasi-religious autonomy. In order to achieve this, I will be exploring how the Requiem fits within certain concepts and movements which occur around the turn of the nineteenth century. Mozart’s death in December 1791 provides an ideal starting point to explore this intricate dialogue.

The news of both Mozart’s death and his Requiem Mass became conflated: as early as 27 December 1791 (just 22 days after his death) an anecdote appeared coupling the Requiem and the curious nature of its commission with Mozart’s eventual death, while also creating images of him writing the Requiem for himself ‘often with tears in his eyes’.¹ Legends and myths surrounding the Requiem have been subsumed into western culture for over 200 years, and parsing ‘fact’ from ‘fiction’ has been the task of scholars for generations. Though this ongoing quest for clarity is essential, these more dubious anecdotal sources offer valuable critical information in relation to extra-musical reception. In his recent study of the Requiem, Simon Keefe advocates that we ‘embrace the often murky continuum between fact and fiction’ where this work is concerned.² Doing

¹ Keefe, *Mozart’s Requiem: Reception, Work, Completion*, 14 (Anecdote from *Der Bayerische Landbot*, 27 December 1791).

² *Ibid.* 9.

so allows us to gain a broader understanding of the reception of Mozart's Requiem in a wider cultural context.

There are two examples of documented reception which I would like to highlight from Keefe's book to demonstrate the range of intensity involved. The first example appears in a report in the *Allgemeine musikalische Zeitung* which refers to a military man attending the first Parisian performance of the Requiem in 1804, who reportedly burst into tears shouting 'Almighty God!' as the Introit unfolded.³ The second particularly striking account is of a painter in Dresden who claimed that a performance of the Requiem 'overpowered [him] to such an extent that [...] [he] threw [himself] on the floor and cried and shouted nonsensically'.⁴ The story of the commission being delivered by a grey messenger adds fuel to the fire by suggesting an omen-like aura, galvanising claims that the messenger 'must have been an unusual being, one who stood in close connection with the world beyond or who had been sent to him to announce his death'.⁵ Through the lens of twenty-first-century scholarship such claims are easily dismissed and almost comical, but they do document a desire to link Mozart's death—and indeed his Requiem—with the supernatural. Reactions like these suggest a metanarrative, by which the Requiem gained a certain 'power' in a way which I would argue has not been accorded to any musical work before or since. Such reactions (whether believable or not) cannot be solely accredited to the music alone, but to the broader picture—the legend—of the Requiem and its accumulative effect on a range of communities.

1825 marked the beginning of a widely reported series of claims regarding the authorship of the Requiem known as the *Requiem-Streit*, which was initiated by Jacob Gottfried Weber in an article called 'On the Authenticity of Mozart's Requiem'.⁶ The controversy lasted well over a decade, and by the 1830s the 'fantasy' factor intensified, even finding its way to the stage—Pushkin's play involving Salieri's plot to murder Mozart and present the Requiem as his own being a well-known example of this. This inflation of fabrication draws a parallel with the *Requiem-Streit*: as the 'fandom' community comes to terms with the prospect that the work in which they

³ Ibid. 13.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Ibid. 17 (Rochlitz in the *Allgemeine musikalische Zeitung*).

⁶ Ibid. 49 (*Cäcilia*, 1825).

invest great emotional attachment might not have been created solely by its creator, it deepens the level of obscurity surrounding the Requiem. As these legends and controversies continued to breed, nineteenth-century German attitudes to art—and music in particular—underwent a transformation: art became increasingly synonymous with spirituality. More specifically, it was believed that art embodied the divine on earth, and that experiencing art was akin to taking part in religious ritual. This movement became known as *Kunstreligion*.

In the third speech from his *On Religion: Speeches to its Cultured Despisers* of 1799, Friedrich Schleiermacher describes his wish to intuit 'ever so clearly how the artistic sense, by itself alone, changes into religion',⁷ and that the synergy of art and religion is 'showered [...] with new beauty and holiness and pleasantries softening their original limitedness'.⁸ The movement initially emerged in the form of literature prior to music. Wackenroder's *Heartfelt Outpourings of an Art-Loving Friar* (1797) is most commonly recognised as the origin of this new concept, and is also the work Schleiermacher refers to when he first coins the term *Kunstreligion*.

The idea of *transfiguration* appears to be exclusive to the arrival of *Kunstreligion* in music. Traditionally this is a biblical term, referring to the Transfiguration of Christ upon a mountain. While praying, Jesus begins to shine with bright rays of light, his garments turn a pure white, and the prophets Moses and Elijah appear. The Transfiguration is one of the miracles of Christ, where He becomes a bridge between heaven and earth, a point where human nature meets God, 'the meeting place for the temporal and the eternal'.⁹ Correlating such a profound biblical event with nineteenth-century art is striking to say the least, and represents a very specific state of art reception.

Tracing the progression of *Kunstreligion* through the early nineteenth century, Elizabeth Kramer demonstrates how critical writings on a broad selection of composers consistently comply with one another in defining what exactly a composer's 'divine transfiguration' is: in essence, it is most closely associated with 'immortality' and would only be accredited to a composer if they were dead.¹⁰ Initiation into this select 'club' was retro-

⁷ Schleiermacher, *On Religion: Speeches to Its Cultured Despisers*, 115.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ Lee, *Transfiguration*, 2.

¹⁰ Kramer, "The Idea of Transfiguration in the Early German Reception of Mozart's Requiem," 75–78. She also demonstrates this through Haydn and Beethoven: Initial

spective too, with the likes of Handel, J. S. Bach, Gluck, and Palestrina being included among Mozart, Haydn and Beethoven. For me, this is particularly curious because it demonstrates a very early grouping of a selection of composers who, in time, would become known as founders of the western canon. It also hints at the possibility that the *Kunstreligion* movement played a role in the emergence of the ‘musical work’. In his monograph *Absolute Music and the Construction of Meaning*, Daniel Chua proposes that Romantic ‘music’s purity is self-evident truth; it just is; it needs no historical or external validation’.¹¹ There is a parallel between notions of ‘purity’ and ‘self-evident truth’, and *Kunstreligion*. The very premise of *Kunstreligion* depends on the extent that an appropriate art work has the ability, broadly speaking, to provide those who engage with it an experience comparable to religious devotional participation. Both imply a profound sort of greatness—even superiority—of the ‘work’, to be experienced on its own terms.

Entering into the complex discursive fray with respect to musical meaning presents issues that I will attempt to address in due course. Before moving away from this area, however, I would like to make some final assertions. First, I believe that the role of *Kunstreligion* in the early nineteenth century (and throughout the Romantic era in general) is of much greater historical importance than has been previously acknowledged. Secondly, I challenge Kramer’s statement that ‘early nineteenth-century interest in the authorship of the Requiem grew out of a wider movement of *Kunstreligion*’.¹² Questions of the Requiem’s authorship had existed prior to 1800.¹³ I believe that the arrival of *Kunstreligion* in music was significantly inflected by the sensationalised reception of Mozart’s Requiem. As already stated, the striking notion of transfiguration was not a feature in other areas of *Kunstreligion*. In Mozart’s case, transfiguration came through the romanticised convergence of the Requiem’s ‘profound’ creation and the composer’s untimely and tragic death. The concept of

links between Haydn and transfiguration surfaced in 1810 following his death in 1809. Similarly, Beethoven’s death in 1827 was immediately tied to his transfiguration.

¹¹ Chua, *Absolute Music and the Construction of Meaning*, 5.

¹² Kramer, “The Idea of Transfiguration in the Early German Reception of Mozart’s Requiem,” 73.

¹³ This is perhaps best illustrated by Gottfried Christoph Härtel’s correspondence with Süssmayr in January–February 1800. Keefe provides context on this exchange through pages 174–177 of *Mozart’s Requiem*.

transfiguration quickly spread to other composers, past and present, but the case of Mozart and his Requiem marks a watershed moment in the emergence of this idea.

The aesthetic principles of romanticism, in which an emphasis is placed on the vivid emotional response to art, contrasts with the more rational ideals of the Classical Enlightenment. The widespread dissemination of Mozart's life after 1791 demonstrates this transition very clearly. Though the progression from the Enlightenment into romanticism is the result of many contributing factors (social, political, religious, artistic), I believe the 'story' (the myths and legends, the *Streit*, the 'facts' and 'fictions') of Mozart's Requiem was a major contributing factor in ushering in this new aesthetic appreciation to art, particularly to music. In summary then, the Requiem claims a unique place in music history. It intimates the notion of a composer's 'immortality' through transfiguration, paving the way for romanticism, and plays an indispensable part in the early formation of what is now referred to as the western canon.

Though I do not intend to directly engage with the topic of authorship in this paper, it is impossible to ignore it entirely. At this point in time we are in the privileged position wherein we have established an accurate overview of the extent of Mozart's completion of the Requiem. We know of Eybler's involvement in the Sequenz. And of course, we know much about the involvement of Süssmayr in bringing the Requiem to completion. What we cannot confirm is to what extent Süssmayr was involved with the Requiem prior to Mozart's death, given his claims that he discussed and sung parts through with the composer. However, my motivation for bringing Süssmayr into this seminar is in reaction to a comment by William Ayrton in 1824 (in close proximity of the *Streit*): 'Had another written the Recordare or the Benedictus, the Confutatis, or the Hosanna, he would have burst out of obscurity, and put in his claim on immortality'.¹⁴ The irony of this statement is that he largely cites Süssmayr's work. Furthermore, I would propose that Süssmayr *has* now claimed a slice of immortality through his association with the Requiem. Had he not been involved with the completion of the Requiem, it is quite possible that he would never have achieved posthumous fame. Sure enough, Süssmayr did not 'burst out of obscurity', but he did emerge gradually through the course of musicological history relating to the Requiem.

¹⁴ Keefe, *Mozart's Requiem: Reception, Work, Completion*, 50.

Lydia Goehr argues that music composed before the nineteenth century was a craft, rather than a transcendent work of art.¹⁵ With this in mind, the Requiem becomes something of a red herring: Though its creation sits most definitely in the eighteenth century, the initial experience of an audience would have occurred mostly in the early nineteenth century. The Requiem is undoubtedly one of many examples where this is the case, but it will certainly be the most widespread and disseminated example. A similar scenario might be presented by Mendelssohn's revival of J. S. Bach's Matthew Passion in 1829. However, reception aside, the obscurity and rarity of the matters of authorship will remain one of the Requiem's most intriguing and famous assets. With these unique and obscure elements, what is it that makes this Requiem so captivating? Using Lydia Goehr's theory on the 'work-concept' as a starting point could possibly help address this question as it focuses so closely on this fascinating point of history.

Goehr's general statement that something in the way music was produced, performed and experienced changed around the beginning of the nineteenth century¹⁶ does have a particular resonance: with little specialist knowledge, it is recognised that, for example, the expressive scope of the later piano sonatas and string quartets by Beethoven engages a wider ranging emotional palette which is not yet overtly present in similar works by Haydn or Mozart. Goehr's thesis on the 'work-concept' has useful and interesting implications regarding the Requiem which I will shortly attempt to address. Her theory breaks down into five 'claims', the summary of which is: 1) it is an *open* concept, with *original* and *derivative* employment, 2) it is correlated to the *ideals* of a practice, 3) it is a *regulative* concept, 4) it is *projective*, and finally 5) it is an *emergent* concept.¹⁷ Each of these five claims are elaborated on in great detail, but my intention is not to enter into a point-by-point critique of them. Rather, I want to highlight features of interest.

One aspect that throws up complications is this matter of 'ideals'. Though this area mainly concerns issues of performance practice—the ideal of striving towards perfect compliance with the score—it also clearly concerns the score itself. Though Goehr stipulates that perfect notation

¹⁵ Goehr, *The Imaginary Museum of Musical Works: An Essay in the Philosophy of Music*.

¹⁶ *Ibid.* 119.

¹⁷ *Ibid.* 89–90.

is not a prerequisite in order for the score to function,¹⁸ the Requiem embodies an existential paradox wherein Mozart's intentions are not realised, Süßmayr's intentions are derivative of but not representative of or equal to Mozart's, and as a result, editors, musicologists, performers, and composers alike have been attempting to 'improve' the Requiem for the duration of its existence. It cannot be denied that the Requiem's score has been functioning as an indispensable source, and continues to do so, but there is an ongoing dissatisfaction with it, which sets this work aside from the typical mainstream canon, in which works would tend to be revered. This will no doubt be a ramification of the concept of 'ideals' which perhaps Goehr's definition does not quite extend to consider: just as a perfected performance is an 'ideal', striven for while acknowledging that it cannot be a realisable goal, the quest for the 'perfect' Requiem score is similarly unachievable, but one which will continuously be pursued.

Addressing the first of Goehr's claims is much less straightforward as it relates more to conceptual understanding than to musical works themselves. However, the implication that her open concept is both derivative and original in its use allows one to assess the claim in a musical context. Goehr acknowledges that in order for the work-concept to be an open one, the definition needs to be confined to known, paradigmatic examples with traceable influences and the ability to inspire future events.¹⁹ In essence, her work-concept applies to pieces that fall within the western music tradition, more commonly referred to as the canon. Mozart's place within the canon certainly needs no justification from me, but with particular regards to the Requiem there are two points which I feel are worth considering. Firstly, the Requiem features the prominent contrapuntal influence of J. S. Bach and the use of music from Handel's 'And with his stripes we are healed' and his *Funeral Anthem for Queen Caroline*.²⁰ Though it was not uncommon to model one's work on others, it is surely no coincidence that Mozart consciously modelled his Requiem on two of the most significant musical figures of the early eighteenth century, and indeed in western music history. Whether this was done as a pragmatic compositional exercise, or perhaps as a mark of respect, Mozart deliberately interweaves J. S. Bach and Handel into the fabric of his Requiem. In turn, later settings of

¹⁸ Ibid. 101.

¹⁹ Ibid. 93.

²⁰ Other influences are present too, such as that of Michael Haydn's Requiem.

the Requiem by Verdi and Brahms, for example, also demonstrate a degree of conscious retrospect, with Mozart's influence being quite obvious, thus indicating that the Requiem was very much considered part of the 'heritage' of the canon.

The second point once more concerns Süssmayr's role in the completion of the Requiem, as it seems wrong to focus exclusively on Mozart just because we are limiting ourselves to thinking canonically. Though it is without question that a main motivating factor for the posthumous completion was financially driven, Constanze's desire to finish the Requiem indicates an initial historical value of the work in itself. The fact that Eybler and Süssmayr were the first to attempt this is not what's important: at some point after Mozart's death someone or other would fill this role. This by definition could imply that the Requiem might have already been considered historically significant, even in its unfinished state, a state in which the score could not function, as Goehr implies it must.²¹

My motivation for using Goehr's theory of the work-concept stems from the desire to identify what it is about Mozart's Requiem which has caught the imagination of such a diverse and long-lasting audience. The aim is not to prove whether or not Mozart's Requiem is a 'musical work': I think it's fair to say it has been accepted as one for generations. However, considering theories of the work-concept exclusively in relation to the Requiem is useful as it highlights a number of reasons why it does and does not fit a possible model of a 'musical work'. More fascinatingly, it illustrates that Mozart's Requiem achieved an aesthetic autonomy against the odds, as it were.

It would be disingenuous not to make it clear that Goehr's concept is mainly relevant to the emergence of instrumental music, so its application in relation to the Requiem may not seem entirely fair. The lack of inclusion of other forms presents its own issues, which have been discussed by others at length already. However, what interests me about Goehr's thesis is that it gives much attention to the formation of 'the audience' and how it experienced performance, and the proximity between this and the Requiem's early reception. Goehr's reference to the late eighteenth-century philosopher Herder, who describes the ontological shift in the experience of music at the turn of the century as that of 'religious awe',

²¹ Ibid. 89–90.

draws too strong a parallel to the emergence of *Kunstreligion* to ignore.²² As with *Kunstreligion*, Herder does not refer to 'religion' with regard to religious worship, but rather to a secular 'transcendent religious impulse'. This reinforces my earlier argument that the significance of *Kunstreligion* at the turn of the nineteenth century has perhaps been overlooked.

In an attempt to find cohesion, I am going to conclude by suggesting that the subconscious of a religiously regulated society played a major part in defining music as a transcendent experience.²³ Though Goehr's thesis does not mention *Kunstreligion* directly, I believe any concept of the nineteenth-century 'work' and its application with 'concert' or 'instrumental' music is derived from this earlier movement; a movement, which as suggested before, I believe Mozart's Requiem was central to the development of. This might, in part, address why the Requiem has achieved a quasi-religious aesthetic autonomy. Though it is apparent that Mozart's Requiem occupies a sort of paradoxical state, in which it clearly associates with but does not fit definitions of a musical 'work'. One possible conclusion from this is that Mozart's Requiem surpasses the standard nineteenth-century 'musical work' because of its permanently unfinished state of flux and the imaginative stories which have become part of the substance of the work. Because of this state of flux, the Requiem—as a work and as a story—is constantly being reshaped and moulded to suit multiple functions. In doing so, it transcends any conceivable intention of Mozart's or indeed of Süssmayr's. In essence, the Requiem embodies an ineffable quality of music and represents an extra-musical mystique from its time and that—I believe—is the cause of this work's lasting popularity and cultural importance which has extended into a quasi-religious autonomy.

²² Ibid. 157.

²³ Erauw, "Canon Formation: Some More Reflections on Lydia Goehr's Imaginary Museum of Musical Works," 109–115. I had arrived at this conclusion independently of Erauw's paper, only discovering it at a later stage of the lifecycle of this work, though I want to acknowledge it as it is a thoroughly excellent article.

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AUTHOR'S NOTE

This paper was written as part of an MMus(R) degree at the University of Glasgow. It has been presented at the BFE/RMA Research Students' Conference Bangor 2016, the postgraduate research seminar series at the University of Glasgow, and in other forums.

This paper was the beginning of what I had hoped to be a much larger research effort on Mozart and religion, though this never transpired. Naturally, there is much scope for development. It is being made publicly available now as I continue to receive requests for it. Other than matters of typography and style, the text is unchanged from its original 2016 form.

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